

Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings

Report on analytics and interoperability implementation

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Authors:	CIMNE - Stoyan Danov, Jordi Cipriano, Daniel Pérez

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Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
EnEffectConsult	Stanislav Andreev
Subcontractor (CIMNE)	Mike Barker

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary	6
2	Background	6
3	Introduction	7
4	Data processing and analytics	7
4.1	Common data processing operations.....	10
4.2	Benchmarking of buildings	12
4.3	Assessment and benchmarking of EEMs.....	15
5	Interoperability.....	21
5.1	Acquisition of data from external systems.....	21
5.2	Exposing data from EN-TRACK to external systems	21
6	Conclusions and next steps	22
7	Annex 1. EN-TRACK data analytics library	23
8	Annex 3. Results validation	26

List of figures

<i>Figure 1. EN-TRACK data processing and analytics steps.....</i>	8
<i>Figure 2. Data processing: (a) benchmarking of buildings; (b) benchmarking of EEMs.9</i>	
<i>Figure 3. EN-TRACK outliers detection procedure.</i>	11
<i>Figure 4. Evaluation of single EEM.</i>	18
<i>Figure 5. Evaluation of a project with several EEMs.</i>	19
<i>Figure 6. EN-TRACK API (screenshot).....</i>	22

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CDD	Cooling Degree Days
DEEP	De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measure
HDD	Heating Degree Days
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M&V	Measurement and Verification

1 Executive summary

The document reports on the implementation of the data analytics and interoperability of EN-TRACK. It provides an overview of the implemented functionalities, putting emphasis on the specific assumptions in the processing and calculation of the results, aiming to facilitate their understanding and interpretation by the users. References to the source code and detailed technical documentation published in open online repositories are provided.

The data processing implementation comprises of a set of software components integrated into an R software library (<https://github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/retrack>) that are reusable and combinable for performing variety of tasks including among others data collection, data harmonisation, pre-processing and calculation of KPIs. A full list of the functions in the library is provided in Annex 1. These common utility components are combined into two data processing pipelines written in Python that produce the results presented in the EN-TRACK web application (https://github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/entrack_services).

The first pipeline produces the benchmarking of buildings, and the second one provides the assessment and benchmarking of EEMs. The descriptions of both pipelines include details of the data-driven models and the particularities in their application for benchmarking and assessment of EEMs, including the specific assumptions.

In the context of interoperability, the acquisition of data from the eQuad and DEEP platforms, and the exposure of EN-TRACK data to external systems, is addressed through comments and referencing of the implemented Application Programming Interfaces.

All the software documentation will be maintained and updated in the respective repositories to keep track of any new functionality implemented in EN-TRACK. It is important to note that the open software library *retrack* developed in the project promotes the reusability of its components in other data-driven initiatives. The continuous gathering of data by the project platform will enable wider evaluation of the existing tools and their further upgrading in the future.

2 Background

EN-TRACK, which stands for *Energy Efficiency Performance-Tracking Platform for Benchmarking Savings and Investments in Buildings*, is a project that seeks to address a number of key barriers holding back greater investments in building energy efficiency.

The core objectives of the project, which is funded through the European Union (EU) Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 885395, are to:

- enable massive gathering of data on the before-and-after performance of energy efficiency measures in buildings;
- create a continuous data collection process through structured engagement with stakeholders;

- adopt standard data descriptions that align with current international standards and existing data platforms, notably the De-Risking Energy Efficiency Platform (DEEP); and,
- create a self-sustaining solution that continues to be viable after the completion of the project.

The project produces a set of performance indicators for buildings and energy efficiency investments and offers benchmarking services. This document reports on the implementation of the data analytics supporting the services and builds on the previous deliverables from Work packages 1 and 2.

3 Introduction

The objective of EN-TRACK is to gather large scale data on energy performance of buildings and EEM implemented in buildings and to offer benchmarking services supporting de-risking of energy efficiency investments based on data processing and analytics.

The interoperability with external platforms is also a key objective, as it enables the collection of data on the one hand and, on the other hand, provides joint services with other existing tools on the market. In this way, it offers additional value by helping to consolidate an ecosystem of complementary tools for supporting energy efficiency financing.

The basic output of EN-TRACK is benchmarking of energy performance of buildings and evaluation and benchmarking of energy efficiency measures. This is supported with data analysis and processing.

The objective of this report is to provide information on how the results in the EN-TRACK platform are produced, focusing specifically on the implementation of data analytics for M&V of savings, calculation of KPIs, and benchmarking. The report addresses also the implementation of the interoperability with external systems.

In order to keep the document accessible for the general public, the analytical processing implementation in the EN-TRACK platform is presented at high level, while more technical details are provided in annexes and through technical documentation references.

4 Data processing and analytics

This section presents the implementation of data processing and analytics components of the EN-TRACK platform. The implementation has been based on the requirements and specifications defined in previous deliverables. Figure 1 illustrates the main data processing steps, explaining the operations, and referencing the respective deliverables that provide the specifications.

Figure 1. EN-TRACK data processing and analytics steps.

The different software components are implemented as subroutines in the R software library *rentrack* providing specific functionalities that can be reused for the data analytics tasks in EN-TRACK.

The *rentrack* library is published in a public repository on GitHub:

<https://github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/rentrack>

The components are then integrated into two main pipelines coded in Python that execute the calculations to produce the particular results shown in the EN-TRACK web application. Pipeline A1, Figure 2 (a), produces the set of KPIs for benchmarking of buildings. Pipeline A2, Figure 2 (b), produces the set of KPIs for benchmarking of EEMs.

Figure 2. Data processing: (a) benchmarking of buildings; (b) benchmarking of EEMs.

The pipelines code is published on GitHub:
https://github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/entrack_services

Both pipelines share some common steps in the data preparation and modelling techniques but have some differences in application due to the different objectives of the analysis. Pipeline A1 aims to produce KPIs for the building that allow the changes of its performance over the time to be assessed while pipeline A2 aims to assess the savings from the EEMs applied to buildings and to produce KPIs for their comparison.

The following subsections provide more detail about the different data processing steps for benchmarking of buildings and EEMs. The description starts with the generic and common processing operations for data preparation that are shared between both pipelines and continues with the particular modelling and processing steps in each pipeline.

4.1 Common data processing operations

Data collection

EN-TRACK collects data from different data sources by means of automated data transfer through API, upload of data from files and manual data entry through the EN-TRACK user interface. The specific data sources and data collection procedures are described in D1.2.

The documentation and the python code of the procedures for the implemented data sources can be found in the public GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/retrack>

Data harmonisation

The data harmonisation in the EN-TRACK platform is achieved by alignment of all data from the external data sources to the EN-TRACK data model (see D1.1). This implies operations of mapping and transformation into the internal harmonised format, and their allocation in the harmonised databases (see D2.1), which serve as input for the further data processing.

Detection of disruptive periods

This procedure aims to analyse the energy consumption time series and detect disruptive, atypical periods, that should not be considered in the training phases of the baseline model. An example of a disruptive period is the COVID-19 lockdown when energy consumption in tertiary buildings changed due to radically different occupancy and activity patterns.

The internal model used to detect an alleged disruptive period considers the daily consumption and the non-linear relationships between weekdays and the daily-averaged outdoor temperature. This functionality is implemented in the "detect_disruptive_period()" function of retrack library.

Detection of consumption outliers

An important data preparation step before the modelling phase is to detect consumption measurements which are presumably wrong, either due to communication, storage or measuring issues. The estimation of the outliers in energy consumption time series is based on a quantile regression model that uses calendar features as input variables. Thus, the input data required for this algorithm is the consumption time series, because the calendar features can be inferred from the time stamps information of the input time series. All measures outside the prediction interval defined are considered as an outlier, and this interval is configured based on parameters set in every service execution.

The next figure explains the model evaluation and prediction of the prediction intervals when the model is fitted using a moving time window of 1 week. In the case of a consumption time series of monthly frequency, the window considers 12 months.

Figure 3. EN-TRACK outliers detection procedure.

Detection of holidays

The implemented function detects holiday periods in buildings with highly seasonal patterns by analysing the density-function turn points contained in the daily-aggregated consumption time series. This process is performed to identify over-represented low-consumption days. In addition, post-processing is done to address additional constraints related to holiday periods. This analysis only considers days without any outlier or disruptive period detected during previous steps in this pipeline.

The identification of the holidays for days with outliers is performed by predicting a classifier model that is based on a random forest model that uses holidays detected in the first procedure as output and their related day of the week, day of the year and month as input features.

For more information, check the "detect_holidays_in_tertiary_buildings()" function in `rentrack`.

Interpolations of the outdoor temperature

The implemented data transformations are interpolations, where necessary to fill small gaps in the outdoor temperatures time series that might affect the modelling in the training or prediction phase. Considering the continuity of the outdoor temperature signal, when small gaps (<12 hours) occur, a linear interpolation between the two last known temperatures is performed.

Calculation of Heating and Cooling Degree Days

Heating degree days (HDD) and cooling degree days (CDD) are meteorological indices used to quantify the demand for heating or cooling in a building, respectively. They are calculated based on temperature data and are particularly valuable for longer time intervals (monthly or lower frequency) because they provide a means to account for seasonal variations in temperature and energy consumption.

The implementation in EN-TRACK follows the methodology defined in D1.3. The base temperature for HDD is 15.5°C and for CDD is 22°C.

The function that implements this calculation is: "degree_days()".

4.2 Benchmarking of buildings

This section outlines the specific implementation of the data processing and analytics for the pipeline A1 corresponding to the benchmarking of buildings. This includes the adopted benchmarking approach, the implementation of the data-driven modelling of the energy consumption, and the calculation of KPIs.

There are two types of benchmarking of buildings implemented in EN-TRACK, longitudinal and cross-sectional. The benchmarking is applied and visualised similarly for all KPIs calculated for buildings and EEMs. Please refer to D1.3 for detailed definition of the KPIs and to D2.2 for the implementation in the web application user interface.

Longitudinal benchmarking involves assessing and comparing a building's energy performance over time. In this approach, the energy consumption of a particular building is tracked and analysed across multiple periods, typically spanning several years or months. The primary focus is understanding the building's energy trends, identifying seasonal variations, and evaluating the overall impact of energy-saving measures implemented over time. Longitudinal benchmarking is instrumental in monitoring the effectiveness of energy efficiency initiatives and gauging the building's progress toward sustainability goals. **The longitudinal benchmarking in EN-TRACK is supported by data-driven baseline models of the building's energy consumption built over a period of time that serves as a reference for comparison (baseline). Depending on the available energy consumption data granularity, an hourly or monthly data model is used.**

Cross-sectional benchmarking revolves around comparing the energy performance of multiple buildings at a specific time. Instead of studying the same building over different periods, cross-sectional benchmarking involves analysing a group of diverse buildings to identify high and low performers. This method enables facility managers, policymakers, and stakeholders to gain insights into the energy efficiency of various buildings within a comparable context. Cross-sectional benchmarking facilitates the identification of best practices and allows buildings with suboptimal energy performance to learn from the top-performing ones. **The cross-sectional benchmarking in EN-TRACK aims to present the most actual data for in the building comparatives. For this reason, the KPIs used in the cross-sectional benchmarking are calculated for the last full year with available energy consumption data for the building.**

Data-driven models

The data-driven models represent the behaviour of a dependent variable during certain period of time in function of independent variables that demonstrate statistically significant influence on the dependent variable. These models can be used for prediction and in this context their predictions are called "counterfactual", as they estimate the dependant variable as if it responds in the same way to the independent variables as it does in the training period. The underlying assumption is that the system (in our case – the building) represented by the dependent variable hasn't changed. The counterfactual

prediction is the basis for comparing the performance of buildings in different periods in longitudinal benchmarking, and for attributing the savings to EEMs in Measurement and Verification procedures.

In EN-TRACK the models are trained on data from certain periods are used to predict the energy consumption of a building in function of parameters such as external temperature, occupancy, day of the week, etc.

By assessing the influence of the external temperature over the consumption, the models are also able to split the overall consumption into Heating, Cooling, and Baseload consumption, thus providing important insights into the use of energy in the buildings.

Hourly baseline model

The hourly baseline model of EN-TRACK is a data-driven model built on the **random forest machine modelling technique**, proven to be effective in capturing complex relationships and patterns in the data. The model is trained over specific periods defined as baseline and is then used to predict the hourly counterfactual energy consumption for periods outside the baseline period. The initial data required by the model, the output, and settings are as follows.

Input features:

- Hourly time series of the outdoor temperature
- The hour of the day,
- The day of the year,
- The day of the week,
- A Boolean feature determining if a day is a holiday or not.

Output feature:

- Hourly time series of the energy consumption.

All data is directly introduced to the "RandomForest()" function, according to the input-output description.

Setting parameters and assumptions for the calculation in EN-TRACK

- Outliers detection: The actual consideration of the prediction interval considers the prediction of the 10th percentile multiplied by 0.25 for the lower interval, and the prediction of the 90th percentile multiplied by 1.75 for the high interval. The window of training for the calendar features model is one month.
- Disruptive periods detection: The date intervals configured to detect the disruptive periods are between 2020-03-14 and 2020-03-23 for the lower interval, and 2020-06-21 and 2022-08-30 for the higher interval.
- Selection of baseline periods: 2019 and 2021 are the years selected as baseline period. Furthermore, input and output features of the model need to cover more than a 75% of the period to execute the training process of the counterfactual model. If no model can be trained, the corresponding KPIs are not estimated.

- Time-aggregation of the KPIs: When more than a 75% of the period is covered, the time-aggregation of the KPIs time series is done and normalised to the theoretical length of the period. For instance, the value of a KPI in a specific year is only computed when more than a 75% of the period is covered for that year. Then, the KPI value is normalised to a theoretical period of one year.

Monthly baseline model

The monthly baseline model of EN-TRACK is a data-driven model built on the **random forest machine modelling technique**, proven to be effective in capturing complex relationships and patterns in the data. The model is trained over specific periods defined as its baseline and is then used to predict the monthly counterfactual energy consumption for periods outside the baseline period. The initial data required by the model, the output, and settings are as follows.

Input features:

- Monthly time series of the heating degree days,
- Monthly time series of the cooling degree days,
- The month of the year,
- The number of weekend days,
- The number of workweek days,
- The number of days that are supposed to be holidays

Output feature:

- Monthly time series of the energy consumption.

All data is directly introduced to the "RandomForest()" function, according to the input-output description.

Setting parameters and assumptions for the calculation in EN-TRACK

- Outliers detection: The actual consideration of the prediction interval considers the prediction of the 10th percentile multiplied by 0.5 for the lower interval, and the prediction of the 90th percentile multiplied by 1.5 for the high interval. The window of training for the calendar features model is one year.
- Disruptive periods detection: A default disruptive period is considered in all cases: from march 2020 to august 2020, both included.
- Selection of baseline periods: 2019 and 2021 are the years selected as baseline period. Furthermore, input and output features of the model need to cover more than a 75% of the period to execute the training process of the counterfactual model. If no model can be trained, the corresponding KPIs are not estimated.
- Time-aggregation of the KPIs: When more than a 75% of the period is covered, the time-aggregation of the KPIs time series is done and normalised to the theoretical length of the period. For instance, the value of a KPI in a specific year is only

computed when more than a 75% of the period is covered for that year. Then, the KPI value is normalised to a theoretical period of one year.

Calculation of KPIs for benchmarking of buildings

EN-TRACK provides cross-sectional and longitudinal benchmarking of buildings over a variety of KPIs. For detailed information, refer to D1.3. The cross-sectional benchmarking is offered openly as it is anonymised, and the longitudinal benchmarking is offered for registered users over their own buildings.

The benchmarking categories include energy use and savings, energy cost, and emissions.

4.3 Assessment and benchmarking of EEMs

This section outlines the specific implementation of the data processing and analytics for the pipeline A2 corresponding to the assessment and benchmarking of EEMs. This includes the benchmarking approach, the implementation of the data-driven modelling for assessment of the EEMs, and the calculation of KPIs.

The benchmarking of EEMs in EN-TRACK uses only the cross-sectional approach, comparing various KPIs for single EEM from the same type.

Hourly measurement and verification model

This model is used for the assessment of the EEMs. It is similar to the hourly baseline model in that it is a data-driven model built on the **random forest machine modelling technique**. It differs in that it follows a specific workflow and settings. The model is initially trained using data collected before the implementation of each EEM project. Subsequently, this trained model is employed to predict the hourly counterfactual energy consumption for the period after the EEM project has been implemented. The initial data required by the model, the output, and settings are as follows.

Input features:

- Hourly time series of the outdoor temperature
- The hour of the day,
- The day of the year,
- The day of the week,
- A Boolean feature determining if a day is a holiday or not.

Output feature:

- Hourly time series of the energy consumption.

All data is directly introduced to the "RandomForest()" function, according to the input-output description.

Setting parameters and assumptions for the calculation in EN-TRACK

- Outliers detection: The actual consideration of the prediction interval considers the prediction of the 10th percentile multiplied by 0.25 for the lower interval, and the prediction of the 90th percentile multiplied by 1.75 for the high interval. The window of training for the calendar features model is one month.
- Disruptive periods detection: The date intervals configured to detect the disruptive periods are between 2020-03-14 and 2020-03-23 for the lower interval, and 2020-06-21 and 2022-08-30 for the higher interval.
- The selection of baseline and evaluation periods are furthermore explained in section Assessment of EEMs.

Monthly Measurement & Verification model

This model is used for the assessment of the EEMs. It is similar to the monthly baseline model, it is a data-driven model built on the **random forest machine modelling technique**. It differs in that it follows a specific workflow and settings. The model is initially trained using data collected before the implementation of each EEM project. Subsequently, this trained model is employed to predict the hourly counterfactual energy consumption for the period after the EEM project has been implemented. The initial data required by the model, the output, and settings are as follows.

Input features:

- Monthly time series of the heating degree days,
- Monthly time series of the cooling degree days,
- The month of the year,
- The number of weekend days,
- The number of workweek days,
- The number of days that are supposed to be holidays

Output feature:

- Monthly time series of the energy consumption.

All data is directly introduced to the "RandomForest()" function, according to the input-output description.

Setting parameters and assumptions for the calculation in EN-TRACK

- Outliers detection: The actual consideration of the prediction interval considers the prediction of the 10th percentile multiplied by 0.5 for the lower interval, and the prediction of the 90th percentile multiplied by 1.5 for the high interval. The window of training for the calendar features model is one year.

- Disruptive periods detection: A default disruptive period is considered in all cases: from march 2020 to august 2020, both included.
- The selection of baseline and evaluation periods are furthermore explained in section Assessment of EEMs.

Assessment of EEMs

The application of Energy Efficiency Measures (EEMs) produces energy, financial, and emissions savings and these all are evaluated in EN-TRACK. In the core of the evaluation procedure is the data-driven assessment of the energy savings from the EEMs, which is automated and done through the application of the measurement and verification models for the energy consumption described above. Depending on the available data granularity of the energy consumption, the hourly or monthly model is used.

Once the energy savings are determined, the financial and emissions savings are calculated by using the energy pricing and emissions factors introduced in the system.

EN-TRACK aims to assess the individual effect of each EEM separately and to provide benchmarking for single EEM types. The EEMs are introduced in the system separately but are internally related to renovation projects depending on how close the application dates of the EEM are to each other. Each project might contain one or various EEMs.

Rule for grouping of measures into project:

- An EEM that is applied with a time difference of 180 days or more with respect to any other EEM applied in the same building is assigned to a separate project, a single EEM project.
- EEMs that are applied in less than 180 days respect to any other EEM applied in the same building are grouped into the same project, a project with several EEMs.

The two types of projects require different procedures to assess the individual EEM performances in them. While the assessment of single EEM projects is more straightforward, assessing the individual contribution of each EEM in a project containing several requires additional processing (and assumptions).

The assessment is done in two steps: first, assessment of the saving from the project in overall and second, splitting the overall saving to the individual EEMs in the project. The two scenarios are described below.

Scenario 1: A single EEM project

This is the situation when a building renovation project contains a single EEM and there are no other known actuations affecting the building performance 180 days before and 180 days after the application of the EEM. This situation is represented in Figure 3.

Figure 4. Evaluation of single EEM.

The saving from the EEM is assessed through a counterfactual M&V model as follows. The model is initially trained using data collected before implementing each EEM. Subsequently, this trained model is employed to predict the counterfactual energy consumption for the period after the EEM project has been implemented. Depending on the available data, hourly or monthly model is used.

The following settings in the calculation are adopted to guarantee consistent results with acceptable quality:

- Minimum days with energy consumption before the EEM = 180
- Minimum days in the training period without outliers = 40
- Minimum days with energy consumption after the EEM = 180
- Maximum days with energy consumption after the EEM = 365

Even if more data exists, the assessment will consider only this maximum value.

If these conditions are not fulfilled, the EEM is not assessed.

Scenario 2: A project with several EEMs

This is the situation when a project contains two or more EEM that are applied in less than 180 days from each other or simultaneously. The situation is represented in Figure 4, see project 2 (EEM2+EEM3).

Figure 5. Evaluation of a project with several EEMs.

The evaluation of saving is done for the overall project by applying M&V model trained over the period before the first EEM in the project and predicting the counterfactual consumption in the period after the last EEM in the project. In a next step, the saving from the EEM project is split among individual EEMs according to the following rules, depending on if the investment amount is available as a lumped sum for the overall project or by each individual EEM in the project.

Option 1: The investment is available for each individual EEM in the project

The individual saving for each individual measure EEM_i in the project is calculated as:

$$S_i = S_p \cdot \frac{\frac{S'_i}{I'_i} I_i A_i C_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n (\frac{S'_i}{I'_i} I_i A_i C_i)}$$

where ‘S’ is the total energy saving, ‘i’ corresponds to a specific i-th individual EEM, ‘p’ corresponds to the whole project of EEMs, ‘n’ is the total number of individual EEMs, ‘I’ is the investment, ‘A’ is the affected gross floor area in the building, ‘C’ is 1 if the measured property component of the consumption (total, heating, cooling or baseload) is related with the typology of a specific individual EEM, 0 if no.

The settings for indicating the affectation of the consumption property component by the type of EEM (level 1 of the EEM taxonomy) are provided below in a form of dictionary:

"EEMMeasuredPropertyComponents": {

"BuildingFabricMeasure": ["Heating", "Cooling", "Baseload", "Total"],

"LightingMeasure": ["Baseload", "Total"],

"RenewableGenerationMeasure": ["Heating", "Cooling", "Baseload", "Total"],

"HVACAndHotWaterMeasure": ["Heating", "Cooling", "Baseload", "Total"],

"ElectricPowerSystemMeasure": ["Heating", "Cooling", "Baseload", "Total"],

"default": ["Heating", "Cooling", "Baseload", "Total"] }

The ratio ' S'_i/I'_i ' is specific for each EEM type and represents the average ratio of annual savings (kWh) and investment (€) derived from previous data available in the EN-TRACK data. In case the ratio ' S'_i/I'_i ' is not available for some EEM in the project, it is supposed to be the same for all EEM types and thus not considered in the equation.

Option 2: Only the overall project investment is available

$$S_i = S_p \cdot \frac{\frac{S'_i}{I'_i} A_i C_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{S'_i}{I'_i} A_i C_i}$$

In this option, as the individual investment for the EEMs ' I'_i ' is not available, it is eliminated as a weight factor from the formula.

The following settings for the assessments in Scenario 2 are implemented:

- Force assessments by single EEM = true

The assessment is done for the whole EEM project and the effect split to individual EEMs.

- Force assessments by single EEM = false

The assessment is done for the whole EEM project only.

Calculation of KPIs for benchmarking of EEMs

EN-TRACK provides cross-sectional benchmarking of EEMs for a variety of KPIs. For detailed information, refer to D1.3. The KPIs are conceptually grouped in energy, cost, and emissions savings. Another group of KPIs comprises the financial indicators for the investment.

In the core of the savings related KPIs is the assessment of the energy saving obtained by the EEM by using the counterfactual M&V models described in the previous section. The rest of the KPIs related to cost, emissions, and finance are calculated from the set by the user energy cost, emission coefficients, and discount rates. Refer to D1.3 for details.

5 Interoperability

The interoperability is the capability of systems to share information and be used together.

The interoperability of EN-TRACK with external systems has a twofold objective: to enable new sources of data for the EN-TRACK databases and to expose the benchmarking results of EN-TRACK to other systems in the context of providing joint services.

5.1 Acquisition of data from external systems

The acquisition of data from external systems related to energy efficiency investments is intended to enrich the EN-TRACK benchmarking database. The implementation has focused on the eQuad and DEEP platforms, following the requirements and specifications provided in deliverable D1.5. For this purpose the existing APIs of eQuad and DEEP have been used. The particularities of both cases and the specific solutions are outlined below.

Acquisition of data from eQuad

The implementation for eQuad aims the acquisition of granular and anonymised data from energy efficiency projects evaluated in eQuad. For this the existing API of eQuad has been used.

The eQuad platform has been implemented as a RESTful web service with the following endpoint URL:

<https://app.equadcapital.com/>

The RESTful web service exposes a set of resources such as files, html pages and contractors' data by using the HTTP protocol. The default resource representation format of the API is JSON.

The implementation in EN-TRACK uses the "project service" of the eQuad RESTful API for acquisition of individual projects data that have been previously validated.

Acquisition of data from DEEP

The implementation aims the acquisition of anonymised benchmarking data from DEEP. The existing API of DEEP has been used:

<https://deep.ec.europa.eu/apidoc/>

5.2 Exposing data from EN-TRACK to external systems

EN-TRACK has implemented RESTful API for exporting data and benchmarking results to external systems. These functionalities follow the specifications of D1.5 and are:

- Exporting granular projects data from EN-TRACK to external systems conditioned on the generation of a token from the data owner, thus giving consent for the export of the data.
- Exporting anonymous benchmarking data for the KPIs produced in EN-TRACK.

The documentation of the APIs is provided in a repository of CIMNE:

<https://api-dev.kube.tech.beegroup-cimne.com/#/>

```
{
  "results": [
    {
      "ac": "avoidance cost",
      "creationDate": "dd-mm-yyyTHH:MM:ssZ",
      "description": "project description",
      "irr": "internal rate of return",
      "name": "project",
      "nic": "normalized investment cost",
      "npv": "net present value",
      "npvq": "net present value quotient",
      "payback": "simple payback",
      "pi": "profitability index",
      "projectCountry": "BG",
      "projectCurrency": {
        "currencyCode": "EUR",
        "currencySign": "€"
      },
      "sites": [
        {
          "address": "street name",
          "ecm": [
            {
              "_ecmId": {
                "taxonomyLevel1": "taxonomy level 1",
                "taxonomyLevel2": "taxonomy level 2",
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 6. EN-TRACK API (screenshot)

6 Conclusions and next steps

In conclusion, the data-driven services and the retrack analytics tools implemented within EN-TRACK as open source software offer significant promise for the fields of energy consumption benchmarking and the assessment of energy efficiency measures. These tools empower users to glean valuable insights from data, facilitating informed decision-making and strategic energy management. Moreover, the retrack library not only provides a robust framework for analytics but also promotes the reusability of analytical components. This echoes the principles of the data ontology within EN-TRACK, which seeks to unify highly diverse datasets into a common language, enhancing data interoperability. Retrack aspires to serve as an interoperable toolbox for various analytical service components related to energy in buildings.

This synergy between data harmonisation and analytics reusability is pivotal. It streamlines processes, fosters collaboration, and amplifies the longevity and versatility of data-driven initiatives. Looking ahead, these integrated capabilities are poised to play an increasingly vital role in shaping the future of energy management and sustainability, supporting organisations in their quest for more efficient and environmentally responsible energy practices. Future steps in ENTRACK services aim to gather more data from real buildings and leverage existing evaluations using the actual tools to develop an upgraded and a more complete version of the services.

7 Annex 1. EN-TRACK data analytics library

A list of the functions implemented in retrack are:

Function name	Explanation of functionality
<u>add_item_to_rdf</u>	Add triplet to and RDF object
<u>align_time_grid</u>	Align a time series to an specific time grid.
<u>append_cost_to_sensor</u>	Append the cost and price to some energy time series sensor
<u>append_emissions_to_sensor</u>	Append the emissions to some energy time series sensor
<u>ARX</u>	AutoRegressive Model with eXogenous variables
<u>AR term</u>	Calculate the autoregressive term
<u>boxcox_transformation</u>	Box-Cox transformation
<u>calculate_indicator</u>	Calculate time series KPI.
<u>calculate_indicator_not_aggregable_by_time</u>	Calculate a KPI not aggregable by time.
<u>calendar_components</u>	Time decomposition
<u>classification_dlc</u>	Daily load curve classification
<u>clean_ts_integrate</u>	Converts time series to instantaneous
<u>clustering_dlc</u>	Daily load curves clustering
<u>compute_device_aggregator_formula</u>	Compute the specified formula of a device aggregator
<u>data_transformation_wrapper</u>	Wrapper to execute the data transformations in the modelling framework
<u>decodeBinFromValue</u>	Encode value to binary representation
<u>decodeValueFromBin</u>	Decode binary representation to value
<u>degree_days</u>	Degree days with time aggregation
<u>degree_raw</u>	Degree days without time aggregation
<u>detect_disruptive_period</u>	Detect disruptive periods in consumption time series.
<u>detect_holidays_in_tertiary_buildings</u>	Detect holidays in consumption time series
<u>detect_profiled_data</u>	Detect profiled days in data
<u>detect_static_min_max_outliers</u>	Detect min-max outliers in static data.
<u>detect_static_reg_exp</u>	Detect reg-exp in static data.
<u>detect_time_step</u>	Detects time step of a time series
<u>detect_ts_calendar_model_outliers</u>	Detect outliers in time series based on a calendar model
<u>detect_ts_calendar_model_outliers_window</u>	Detect outliers in time series based on a calendar model (applied over a window of time)
<u>detect_ts_min_max_outliers</u>	Detect min-max outliers in time series
<u>detect_ts_zscore_outliers</u>	Detect Z-score outliers in time series.
<u>exists_analytical_model</u>	Check if an analytical model exists.
<u>exists_project_model</u>	Check if a project exists.
<u>fill_ts_na</u>	Imputation unknown items in a time series
<u>format_iso_8601z</u>	Parse datetime to ISO 8601 format
<u>fs</u>	Obtain the components of the Fourier Series, in sine-cosine form
<u>fs_components</u>	Fourier series components decomposition
<u>gaMonitor2</u>	Genetic algorithm core monitor
<u>generate_eem_assessment_indicators</u>	Generate the harmonised results of the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEM) assessment
<u>generate_longitudinal_benchmarking_indicators</u>	Generate the harmonised longitudinal benchmarking results
<u>getAttribute</u>	Get single attribute from each of the features in the features list
<u>get_all_buildings_list</u>	Get all building subjects
<u>get_area_building</u>	Get gross floor area of a building
<u>get_buildings_subjects</u>	Get building subjects from a set of building identifier from organisation
<u>get_building_eems</u>	Get the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEMs) subjects from a set of buildings
<u>get_building_identifiers</u>	Calculate the building identifiers

<u>get_building_namespaces</u>	Get namespaces of a building
<u>get_change_point_temperature</u>	Estimate the optimal change point temperature and weather dependance
<u>get_device_aggregators</u>	Get the metadata and time series from a filtered set of device aggregators
<u>get_device_aggregators_metadata</u>	Get the metadata of all device aggregators This function gets all the device aggregators available in a EN-TRACK-harmonised dataset. It also provides metadata with the characteristics of this device aggregators.
<u>get_eem_details</u>	Get the complete metadata from a set of Energy Efficiency Measures (EEMs)
<u>get_eem_lifespan</u>	Get the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEM) lifespan
<u>get_eem_measured_property_components</u>	Get the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEM) measured property components
<u>get_emissions_metadata</u>	Get the emissions metadata
<u>get_KPI_by_building</u>	Get a specific KPI time series from a building
<u>get_KPI_timeseries</u>	Get one Key Performance Indicator (KPI) time series from a certain building.
<u>get_local_min_from_density</u>	Get the local minimums from the probability density function
<u>get_lpf_smoothing_time_scale</u>	Obtain alpha value for low pass filter
<u>get_sensor</u>	Read and prepare a time series
<u>get_sensor_file</u>	Read time series files and generate a list of them split by sensor identifiers
<u>get_sensor_metadata</u>	Get sensor metadata
<u>get_tariff_metadata</u>	Get the energy tariff metadata
<u>get_tz_building</u>	Get timezone of a building
GLM	Generalised Linear Model
<u>hourly_timesteps</u>	Time casting from hours to ISO 8601 timesteps
<u>hyperparameters_tuning</u>	Hyperparameters tuning
<u>inverse_boxcox_transformation</u>	Inverse of the Box-Cox transformation
<u>iso8601_period_to_text</u>	ISO 8601 period to natural text
<u>iso8601_period_to_timedelta</u>	ISO 8601 period to period
<u>lag_components</u>	Lag components
<u>lpf_ts</u>	Low pass filter
<u>make.affinity</u>	Calculate affinity
<u>make.similarity</u>	Calculate similarity matrix
<u>namespace_integrator</u>	Namespace integrator
<u>normalise_daily</u>	Normalise time series by sum of the day
<u>normalise_dlc</u>	Daily load curve normalisation
<u>normalise_range</u>	Normalise time series using min-max range normalisation method
<u>normalise_zscore</u>	Z-Normalisation
<u>optimize</u>	Optimisation function on binary representations of decision variables
<u>opt_boxcox_lambda</u>	Optimiser of the Box-Cox transformation lambda
PenalisedLM	Penalised Linear Regression Model
<u>regression_metrics</u>	Define a set of regression metrics
<u>relative_out_of_boundaries_in_periodogram</u>	Check the ratio of the periodogram out of the boundaries
<u>resample</u>	Resample time series to new ISO 8601 timestep
RLS	Recursive Least Square model
<u>round_up</u>	Round up value or array
<u>similarity</u>	Calculate similarity Exponential Euclidean distance (Frobenius norm) with weighting factor
<u>simulate_prediction_intervals</u>	Simulate the prediction intervals of a linear model
toBin	Binary encoding of a value (integer representation)
<u>weather_dependence_disaggregator</u>	Disaggregate the energy consumption components considering an already trained model and a new set of input data.
<u>write_rdf</u>	Export an RDF to Turtle format (TTL)

To obtain more details about the functions, we strongly recommend to install the library in your computer (<https://www.github.com/BeeGroup-cimne/retrack>) and read the documentation available in R format.

8 Annex 3. Results validation

Validation of the benchmarking results for a single building

A single building is selected for visualising how this pipeline estimates the counterfactual time series, which is necessary, in addition to the real data from the building, to compute all the benchmarking KPIs related to that building. The plots considered in the description of the transformation processes are also related with this building.

- Raw data

Those are the real hourly energy consumption and outdoor temperature of the building in raw format.

- Outliers and disruptive events detected

All red points are days presumably containing outliers in the hourly energy consumption time series and/or are affected by the COVID-19 lockdown periods.

- Holidays detected

All red points are related with low-consumption days, or days that presumably are related with holidays or weekend periods. In buildings with 24-7 activity, no holiday periods are detected.

